

Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47

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Abstract

*We know that we can always write **block-wise magic squares** of any order except for the orders of type p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. On the other hand we can always write **bordered magic squares** of any order. The aims of this work is to combine the both, i.e., **bordered** and **block-wise** magic squares. Whenever possible, we shall write **block-wise** magic squares, otherwise **block-bordered** magic squares. This work is combination of authors previous work in both the direction. The work brings magic squares of orders 10 to 47, either **block-wise** or **block-bordered**. This work is a combinations of author's many previous papers [15, 16, 23, 24, 25]. Future plans are go till magic squares of order 108 [10].*

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1 Introduction

In the previous works [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16], the author worked with **block-wise** constructions of magic squares. The work is from the orders 8 to 45. In each case, all the possibilities are considered. These possibilities are based on divisions of magic squares. The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \tag{1}$$

This formula is applied to all order magic squares. Based on this formula we shall bring **blocks** for the **block-wise** magic squares. That is, whenever is possible, we shall try to bring blocks of equal sum magic squares. In some cases, they are **magic**, **semi-magic**, **pandiagonal**, etc. When the question come to **bimagic** squares, in some cases, we have **semi-bimagic** squares.

On the other hand the idea of **bordered** magic squares is well explained in the work by H.White [7, 8]. Few results in this direction can be seen in author’s work [17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22]. Every magic squares bigger that order 4 can always be written as **bordered** magic square. There are magic squares of type “ p ” or “ $2p$ ”, where “ p ” is a prime numbers, those can’t be written as **block-wise** magic square. In this situation, they can be written as **block-bordered**, i.e., leaving external rows or columns in a uniform way, one can write them as **block-bordered**. There are few works [23, 24, 25] done by author in this direction.

The aim of this work is to combing author’s previous work on **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic squares [15, 16, 23, 24, 25]. It is done from the Section 3 onwards. This work includes magic squares of order 10 to 47. Future plans are to work together with **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic squares. Final aim is to go up to magic square of order 108 [10]. The next work is for the magic squares of orders 48 to 62. The magic squares of orders 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 54, 55, 56, 57 and 60 are constructed as **block-wise**. The magic squares of orders 53, 58, 59, 61 and 62 are constructed as **block-bordered** magic squares.

2 Basic Magic Squares

Below are some magic squares well known in the literature. These are of orders, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. In some cases, these magic squares are **pandiagonal** and or **bimagic**. These are generally used for the constructions of **block-wise magic squares** given in Sections below.

2.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 3 is given by*

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $3k$, $k > 2$.

2.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Below are few basic magic squares already known in the literature.

Example 2.2. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 4.*

		34	34	34	34
	7	12	1	14	34
34	2	13	8	11	34
34	16	3	10	5	34
34	9	6	15	4	34
	34	34	34	34	34

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $4k$, $k > 1$

2.3 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 2.3. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 5 is given by*

		65	65	65	65	65
	1	9	12	20	23	65
65	17	25	3	6	14	65
65	8	11	19	22	5	65
65	24	2	10	13	16	65
65	15	18	21	4	7	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $5k$, $k > 2$

2.4 Magic Square of Order 6

Example 2.4. *Let's consider a magic square of order 6.*

						111
1	35	34	33	2	6	111
30	8	28	9	11	25	111
24	23	15	16	20	13	111
18	14	21	22	17	19	111
7	26	10	27	29	12	111
31	5	3	4	32	36	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $6k$, $k > 1$

2.5 Magic Square of Order 7

Example 2.5. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 7 is given by*

		175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175
175	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $7k$, $k > 2$

2.6 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 8

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 8 is given by

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8 \times (1 + 8^2)}{2} = 260.$$

We can write, $8 := 2^3 = 2 \times 2 \times 2$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 4. In order to get blocks of order 4, we have to divide the total magic sum 260 by 2. Let's see this division:

$$\frac{260}{2} = 130 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4.}$$

Example 2.6. Let's consider a *pan magic square* of order 8 is given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	25	48	1	56	26	47	2	55	260	
260	8	49	32	41	7	50	31	42	260	
260	64	9	40	17	63	10	39	18	260	
260	33	24	57	16	34	23	58	15	260	
260	27	46	3	54	28	45	4	53	260	
260	6	51	30	43	5	52	29	44	260	
260	62	11	38	19	61	12	37	20	260	
260	35	22	59	14	36	21	60	13	260	
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $8k$, $k > 1$

Example 2.7. Let's consider a *pandiagonal bimagic square* of order 8 given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	16	41	36	5	27	62	55	18	260	
260	26	63	54	19	13	44	33	8	260	
260	1	40	45	12	22	51	58	31	260	
260	23	50	59	30	4	37	48	9	260	
260	38	3	10	47	49	24	29	60	260	
260	52	21	32	57	39	2	11	46	260	
260	43	14	7	34	64	25	20	53	260	
260	61	28	17	56	42	15	6	35	260	
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

In this case, the above magic square of order 8 is **bimagic** with **bimagic** sum $Sb_{8 \times 8} := 11180$. Each 2×4 blocks is with equal sum entries as of magic square, i.e., 260

Result 1. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 8 are as follows:*

1. **4 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandiagonal magic square of order 8 is constructed with 4 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4*
2. **Bimagic Square of Order 8:** *The construction of bimagic square of order 8 is well known in the history, and is done by G. Pfeffermann. 1891. In this case, we have a pandiagonal bimagic square of order 8, where the blocks of order 2×4 are of same sum as of magic square of order 8.*

2.7 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 9

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 9 is given by

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9 \times (1 + 9^2)}{2} = 369.$$

We can write, $9 := 3^2 = 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 3. Let's see the division of magic square sum 369 by 3:

$$\frac{369}{3} = 123 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3.}$$

Example 2.8. Let's consider a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 9 is given by

		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
369	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Example 2.9. Let's consider a *bimagic* square of order 9 given by

									369
1	18	23	35	40	48	60	65	79	369
33	38	52	55	72	77	8	13	21	369
62	67	75	6	11	25	28	45	50	369
27	5	10	49	30	44	74	61	69	369
47	34	42	81	59	64	22	3	17	369
76	57	71	20	7	15	54	32	37	369
14	19	9	39	53	31	70	78	56	369
43	51	29	68	73	63	12	26	4	369
66	80	58	16	24	2	41	46	36	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, the above magic square of order 9 is **bimagic** with **bimagic** sum $Sb_{9 \times 9} := 20049$. Each 3×3 block is with equal sum entries as of magic square i.e., 369.

Result 2. *The block-wise constructions magic of squares of order 9 are as follows:*

1. **9 Blocks of Order 3:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 9 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal semi-magic sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
2. **Bimagic Square of Order 9:** *The bimagic square construction is well known in the history by G. Pfeffermann in 1891. In this case, block sums of order 3 are the same.*

The **bimagic squares** of orders 8 and 9 given in examples 2.7 and 2.9 are the classical **bimagic squares** constructed for the first time by G. Pfeffermann [2] in 1819.

Below are three magic squares of order 10, 11 and 14. These shall be used in the constructions of some **block-wise** magic squares. Any, way these magic squares are also written again as **block-bordered** magic squares.

2.8 Magic Square of Order 10

Example 2.10. *Let's consider a magic square of order 10 is given by*

										505
1	80	65	97	39	22	48	86	53	14	505
98	12	9	66	90	74	55	33	41	27	505
47	81	23	79	16	35	94	60	62	8	505
70	57	88	34	2	91	29	15	76	43	505
84	99	52	11	45	68	73	7	30	36	505
13	38	44	10	77	56	82	21	95	69	505
75	46	40	83	28	19	67	92	4	51	505
59	24	96	42	61	3	20	78	37	85	505
26	5	17	58	93	50	31	64	89	72	505
32	63	71	25	54	87	6	49	18	100	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

This magic square shall be used to bring blocks of order 10 in magic squares of orders 20, 30, 40, 50, etc.

2.9 Magic Square of Order 11

Example 2.11. Let's consider a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 11 is given by

		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
	1	13	25	37	49	61	73	85	97	109	121	671
671	108	120	11	12	24	36	48	60	72	84	96	671
671	83	95	107	119	10	22	23	35	47	59	71	671
671	58	70	82	94	106	118	9	21	33	34	46	671
671	44	45	57	69	81	93	105	117	8	20	32	671
671	19	31	43	55	56	68	80	92	104	116	7	671
671	115	6	18	30	42	54	66	67	79	91	103	671
671	90	102	114	5	17	29	41	53	65	77	78	671
671	76	88	89	101	113	4	16	28	40	52	64	671
671	51	63	75	87	99	100	112	3	15	27	39	671
671	26	38	50	62	74	86	98	110	111	2	14	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

This magic square is used in the block-wise construction of magic square of order 33, 44, etc.

2.10 Magic Square of Order 14

Example 2.12. Let's consider a magic square of order 14 is given by

														1379
1	95	191	112	138	78	58	32	17	159	146	178	125	49	1379
147	16	110	176	188	127	87	117	4	53	70	83	38	163	1379
126	162	31	137	172	63	80	6	47	26	97	99	149	184	1379
190	111	150	46	155	115	5	77	34	170	23	96	140	67	1379
164	84	55	12	121	86	29	101	133	62	173	25	186	148	1379
104	10	89	37	21	166	179	154	195	74	44	134	59	113	1379
19	35	132	57	3	153	196	165	180	92	122	51	72	102	1379
45	65	71	90	36	193	152	181	168	119	130	2	103	24	1379
30	43	60	73	94	182	167	194	151	107	7	118	22	131	1379
68	144	156	27	75	48	105	93	120	136	183	42	11	171	1379
81	187	175	114	69	18	135	52	85	14	106	143	160	40	1379
139	174	8	161	142	108	116	15	79	185	39	61	54	98	1379
177	129	123	192	56	33	20	64	100	141	82	158	91	13	1379
88	124	28	145	109	9	50	128	66	41	157	189	169	76	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

The inner 4×4 block is a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 694$. This magic square shall be used to bring blocks of order 14 in magic squares of order 28, 42, 56, etc.

The sections below give results on **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic squares. These results already studied by author in parts. The sections below summarize the results from orders 10 to 53.

3 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 based on magic square of order 8. These are based on the Examples 2.6 and 2.7.

3.1 Blocks of Order 4: Magic Square of Order 8

Example 3.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by*

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88
89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12
11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90
96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5
1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100
93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8
7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94
95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

3.2 Blocks of Order 4: Bimagic Square of Order 8

Example 3.2. The *block-bordered magic square* of order 10 with inner part as bimagic square of order 8 is given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	34	59	54	23	45	80	73	36	88
89	44	81	72	37	31	62	51	26	12
11	19	58	63	30	40	69	76	49	90
96	41	68	77	48	22	55	66	27	5
1	56	21	28	65	67	42	47	78	100
93	70	39	50	75	57	20	29	64	8
7	61	32	25	52	82	43	38	71	94
95	79	46	35	74	60	33	24	53	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

Summarizing, we have following results:

Result 3. *The block-bordered magic square of order 10 is written in two different ways by use of block-wise magic and bimagic squares of order 8. The details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 8, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal bimagic magic square of order 8, where blocks of order 2×8 are of same sum as of magic sum square.*

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4 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

The block-bordered magic square of order 11 is constructed in two different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of order 9 given in Examples 2.8 and 2.9.

4.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 9

Example 4.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 11 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by*

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10
121	42	91	50	47	84	52	40	89	54	1
119	55	41	87	48	43	92	53	45	85	3
117	86	51	46	88	56	39	90	49	44	5
115	60	28	95	65	21	97	58	26	99	7
11	100	59	24	93	61	29	98	63	22	111
13	23	96	64	25	101	57	27	94	62	109
15	78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	107
17	37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	105
19	68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	103
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110

4.2 Blocks of Order 3: Bimagic Square of Order 9

Example 4.2. *The block-bordered magic square of order 11 with inner part as bimagic square of order 9 is given by*

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10
121	29	91	72	95	49	30	62	43	78	1
119	98	52	33	65	46	81	23	85	66	3
117	59	40	75	26	88	69	101	55	36	5
115	73	27	92	31	93	50	79	60	44	7
11	34	96	53	82	63	47	67	21	86	111
13	76	57	41	70	24	89	37	99	56	109
15	90	74	28	48	32	94	42	80	61	107
17	51	35	97	45	83	64	84	68	22	105
19	39	77	58	87	71	25	54	38	100	103
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 4. *The block-bordered magic square of order 11 is written in two different ways by use of block-wise magic and bimagic squares of order 9. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 9, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
2. *Bimagic magic square of order 9, where sum of blocks of order of 3×3 are the same as of magic square.*

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5 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

In this section, we shall present three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 12. First as magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 12 is given by

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12 \times (1 + 12^2)}{2} = 870.$$

We can write, $12 := 2^2 \times 3 = 2 \times 2 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4 and 6. In order to get blocks of orders 3, 4 and 6, we have to divide the magic square sum 870 by 4, 3 and 2. Let's see these divisions:

- (i) $\frac{870}{4} = 217.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{870}{3} = 290 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{870}{2} = 435 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6.

5.1 16 Blocks of Order 3

Example 5.1. 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 constructed using Example 2.1 and arranged according to Example 2.2. It lead us to a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 12 given by

		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
	55	45	68	96	106	83	13	27	2	126	112	137	870	
870	69	56	43	82	95	108	3	14	25	136	125	114	870	
870	44	67	57	107	84	94	26	1	15	113	138	124	870	
870	18	28	5	121	111	134	60	46	71	91	105	80	870	
870	4	17	30	135	122	109	70	59	48	81	92	103	870	
870	29	6	16	110	133	123	47	72	58	104	79	93	870	
870	132	118	143	19	33	8	90	100	77	49	39	62	870	
870	142	131	120	9	20	31	76	89	102	63	50	37	870	
870	119	144	130	32	7	21	101	78	88	38	61	51	870	
870	85	99	74	54	40	65	127	117	140	24	34	11	870	
870	75	86	97	64	53	42	141	128	115	10	23	36	870	
870	98	73	87	41	66	52	116	139	129	35	12	22	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

We observe that it is not possible to have equal magic sums of order 3 as it is impossible to divide magic sum of order 12 by 4, i.e., $870/4=217.5$. In this case, all the 3×3 blocks are magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Sum of each magic square of order 3, lead us to a pandiagonal magic square of order 4 given by

Example 5.2. Sum of magic squares of order 3 given in Example 5.1 lead us to a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 given by

		870	870	870	870
	168	285	42	375	870
870	51	366	177	276	870
870	393	60	267	150	870
870	258	159	384	69	870
	870	870	870	870	870

5.2 9 Blocks of Order 4

Example 5.3. 9 blocks of magic squares of order 4 constructed using Example 2.2 lead us to a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 given by

		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
	55	108	1	126	56	107	2	125	57	106	3	124	870
870	18	109	72	91	17	110	71	92	16	111	70	93	870
870	144	19	90	37	143	20	89	38	142	21	88	39	870
870	73	54	127	36	74	53	128	35	75	52	129	34	870
870	58	105	4	123	59	104	5	122	60	103	6	121	870
870	15	112	69	94	14	113	68	95	13	114	67	96	870
870	141	22	87	40	140	23	86	41	139	24	85	42	870
870	76	51	130	33	77	50	131	32	78	49	132	31	870
870	61	102	7	120	62	101	8	119	63	100	9	118	870
870	12	115	66	97	11	116	65	98	10	117	64	99	870
870	138	25	84	43	137	26	83	44	136	27	82	45	870
870	79	48	133	30	80	47	134	29	81	46	135	28	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{12 \times 12} = 870$. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic square with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 290$.

5.3 4 Blocks of Order 6

Example 5.4. 4 blocks of magic squares of order 6 constructed using Example 2.4 lead us to a magic square of order 12 given by

												870
1	137	136	129	8	24	2	138	135	130	7	23	870
120	32	112	33	41	97	119	31	111	34	42	98	870
96	89	57	64	80	49	95	90	58	63	79	50	870
72	56	81	88	65	73	71	55	82	87	66	74	870
25	104	40	105	113	48	26	103	39	106	114	47	870
121	17	9	16	128	144	122	18	10	15	127	143	870
3	139	134	131	6	22	4	140	133	132	5	21	870
118	30	110	35	43	99	117	29	109	36	44	100	870
94	91	59	62	78	51	93	92	60	61	77	52	870
70	54	83	86	67	75	69	53	84	85	68	76	870
27	102	38	107	115	46	28	101	37	108	116	45	870
123	19	11	14	126	142	124	20	12	13	125	141	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{12 \times 12} := 870$, and all the four blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums $S_{6 \times 6} := 435$.

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 5. *The block-wise constructions of magic square of order 12 is as follows:*

1. **16 Blocks of Order 3:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 12 is constructed with 16 blocks of order 3 with of different magic square sums. Magic sums of order 3 again lead us to a pandigonal magic square of order 4;*
2. **9 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 12 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares 4;*
3. **4 Blocks of Order 6:** *The magic square of order 12 is constructed with 4 blocks of equal sum magic squares of order 6.*

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6 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 13

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 is constructed in two different ways. These are based on **block-wise** magic squares of order 9 given in Examples 2.8 and 2.9.

6.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 9

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 based on magic square of order 9. These are based on the Examples 2.8 and 2.9.

Example 6.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 13 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by*

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	66	115	74	71	108	76	64	113	78	25	166
6	143	79	65	111	72	67	116	77	69	109	27	164
8	141	110	75	70	112	80	63	114	73	68	29	162
10	139	84	52	119	89	45	121	82	50	123	31	160
11	35	124	83	48	117	85	53	122	87	46	135	159
154	37	47	120	88	49	125	81	51	118	86	133	16
152	39	102	97	56	107	90	58	100	95	60	131	18
150	41	61	101	93	54	103	98	59	105	91	129	20
148	43	92	57	106	94	62	99	96	55	104	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

6.2 Blocks of Order 3: Bimagic Square of Order 9

Example 6.2. *The block-bordered magic square of order 13 with inner part as bimagic square of order 9 is given by*

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	53	115	96	119	73	54	86	67	102	25	166
6	143	122	76	57	89	70	105	47	109	90	27	164
8	141	83	64	99	50	112	93	125	79	60	29	162
10	139	97	51	116	55	117	74	103	84	68	31	160
11	35	58	120	77	106	87	71	91	45	110	135	159
154	37	100	81	65	94	48	113	61	123	80	133	16
152	39	114	98	52	72	56	118	66	104	85	131	18
150	41	75	59	121	69	107	88	108	92	46	129	20
148	43	63	101	82	111	95	49	78	62	124	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	8	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 6. *The block-bordered magic square of order 13 is written in two different ways by use of block-wise magic and bimagic squares of order 9. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 9, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
2. *Bimagic magic square of order 9, where sum of blocks of order 3×3 are the same as of sum of magic square.*

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7 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 14

The block-bordered magic square of order 14 is constructed in three different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of order 12 given in Examples 5.1, 5.3 and 29.2.

7.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 12

7.3 Blocks of Order 6: Magic Square of Order 12

14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184
195	27	163	162	155	34	50	28	164	161	156	33	49	2
3	146	58	138	59	67	123	145	57	137	60	68	124	194
193	122	115	83	90	106	75	121	116	84	89	105	76	4
5	98	82	107	114	91	99	97	81	108	113	92	100	192
191	51	130	66	131	139	74	52	129	65	132	140	73	6
177	147	43	35	42	154	170	148	44	36	41	153	169	20
171	29	165	160	157	32	48	30	166	159	158	31	47	26
25	144	56	136	61	69	125	143	55	135	62	70	126	172
173	120	117	85	88	104	77	119	118	86	87	103	78	24
23	96	80	109	112	93	101	95	79	110	111	94	102	174
175	53	128	64	133	141	72	54	127	63	134	142	71	22
21	149	45	37	40	152	168	150	46	38	39	151	167	176
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 7. *The block-bordered magic square of order 14 is written in three different ways by use of block-wise magic square of order 12. The block-wise details are as follows:*

- 1. Pandiagonal magic square of order 12, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums;*
- 2. Pandiagonal magic square of order 12, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
- 3. Magic square of order 12, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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8 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 15

In this section, we shall present two different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 15. The first as magic square formed by 25 blocks **semi-magic** squares of order 3 with equal **semi-magic** sums. The second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 with equal magic sums.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 15 is given by

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15 \times (1 + 15^2)}{2} = 1695.$$

We can write, $15 := 3 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 5. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 1695 by 5 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{1595}{5} = 339 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3;} \\ (ii) \quad \frac{29679}{3} = 565 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 5.}$$

8.1 25 Blocks of Order 3

Example 8.1. 25 blocks of order 3 constructed according to Example 2.1 lead us to a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 given by

9 Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 16

In this section, we shall present two different ways of writing magic squares of order 16. One is **pandiagonal** magic square formed by 16 **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 of equal magic sums. The second is **bimagic** square of order 16.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 16 is given by

$$S_{16 \times 16} := \frac{16 \times (1 + 16^2)}{2} = 2056.$$

We can write, $16 := 4^2 = 4 \times 4$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 4 and 8. Let's see division of 2056 by 4 and 2:

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & \frac{2056}{4} = 514 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;} \\ (ii) \quad & \frac{2056}{2} = 1024 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 8.} \end{aligned}$$

9.1 Pan Magic Square of Order 16

Example 9.1. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 16 constructed according to Example 2.2 is given by

		2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056
	97	192	1	224	98	191	2	223	99	190	3	222	100	189	4	221	2056
2056	32	193	128	161	31	194	127	162	30	195	126	163	29	196	125	164	2056
2056	256	33	160	65	255	34	159	66	254	35	158	67	253	36	157	68	2056
2056	129	96	225	64	130	95	226	63	131	94	227	62	132	93	228	61	2056
2056	101	188	5	220	102	187	6	219	103	186	7	218	104	185	8	217	2056
2056	28	197	124	165	27	198	123	166	26	199	122	167	25	200	121	168	2056
2056	252	37	156	69	251	38	155	70	250	39	154	71	249	40	153	72	2056
2056	133	92	229	60	134	91	230	59	135	90	231	58	136	89	232	57	2056
2056	105	184	9	216	106	183	10	215	107	182	11	214	108	181	12	213	2056
2056	24	201	120	169	23	202	119	170	22	203	118	171	21	204	117	172	2056
2056	248	41	152	73	247	42	151	74	246	43	150	75	245	44	149	76	2056
2056	137	88	233	56	138	87	234	55	139	86	235	54	140	85	236	53	2056
2056	109	180	13	212	110	179	14	211	111	178	15	210	112	177	16	209	2056
2056	20	205	116	173	19	206	115	174	18	207	114	175	17	208	113	176	2056
2056	244	45	148	77	243	46	147	78	242	47	146	79	241	48	145	80	2056
2056	141	84	237	52	142	83	238	51	143	82	239	50	144	81	240	49	2056
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{16 \times 16} = 2056$. All the 4×4 blocks are **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 514$.

9.2 Bimagic Square of Order 16

Example 9.2. A bimagic square of order 16 is given by

																2056
1	154	239	120	23	144	249	98	44	179	198	93	62	165	212	75	2056
232	127	10	145	242	105	32	135	205	86	35	188	219	68	53	174	2056
122	225	152	15	112	247	130	25	83	204	189	38	69	222	171	52	2056
159	8	113	234	137	18	103	256	182	45	92	195	164	59	78	213	2056
46	181	196	91	60	163	214	77	7	160	233	114	17	138	255	104	2056
203	84	37	190	221	70	51	172	226	121	16	151	248	111	26	129	2056
85	206	187	36	67	220	173	54	128	231	146	9	106	241	136	31	2056
180	43	94	197	166	61	76	211	153	2	119	240	143	24	97	250	2056
55	176	217	66	33	186	207	88	30	133	244	107	12	147	230	125	2056
210	73	64	167	200	95	42	177	251	100	21	142	237	118	3	156	2056
80	215	162	57	90	193	184	47	101	254	139	20	115	236	157	6	2056
169	50	71	224	191	40	81	202	132	27	110	245	150	13	124	227	2056
28	131	246	109	14	149	228	123	49	170	223	72	39	192	201	82	2056
253	102	19	140	235	116	5	158	216	79	58	161	194	89	48	183	2056
99	252	141	22	117	238	155	4	74	209	168	63	96	199	178	41	2056
134	29	108	243	148	11	126	229	175	56	65	218	185	34	87	208	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

In this case, the magic and **bimagic** sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2056$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16} := 351576$ respectively. Details of this **bimagic** square can be seen in author's work [20].

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 9. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 16 are as follows:*

1. **16 Blocks of order 4:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 16 is constructed with 16 blocks of pandiagonal magic squares of equal magic sums of order 4.*
2. **16 Blocks of order 4: Bimagic** - *The bimagic square of order 16 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 4.*

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10 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 17

The block-bordered magic square of order 17 is constructed in two different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of order 15 given in Examples 8.1 and 8.2.

10.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 15

16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18
1	218	97	120	219	106	110	220	107	108	221	96	118	222	94	119	289
3	112	225	98	121	215	99	122	213	100	111	223	101	109	224	102	287
5	105	113	217	95	114	226	93	115	227	103	116	216	104	117	214	285
7	68	232	135	69	241	125	70	242	123	71	231	133	72	229	134	283
9	127	75	233	136	65	234	137	63	235	126	73	236	124	74	237	281
11	240	128	67	230	129	76	228	130	77	238	131	66	239	132	64	279
13	38	247	150	39	256	140	40	257	138	41	246	148	42	244	149	277
273	142	45	248	151	35	249	152	33	250	141	43	251	139	44	252	17
271	255	143	37	245	144	46	243	145	47	253	146	36	254	147	34	19
269	188	82	165	189	91	155	190	92	153	191	81	163	192	79	164	21
267	157	195	83	166	185	84	167	183	85	156	193	86	154	194	87	23
265	90	158	187	80	159	196	78	160	197	88	161	186	89	162	184	25
263	203	52	180	204	61	170	205	62	168	206	51	178	207	49	179	27
261	172	210	53	181	200	54	182	198	55	171	208	56	169	209	57	29
259	60	173	202	50	174	211	48	175	212	58	176	201	59	177	199	31
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274

10.2 Blocks of Order 5: Magic Square of Order 15

16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18
1	33	250	62	151	229	63	220	107	136	199	78	190	122	166	169	289
3	152	241	34	243	55	137	211	64	213	100	167	181	79	183	115	287
5	244	48	145	242	46	214	93	130	212	76	184	108	160	182	91	285
7	235	47	256	49	138	205	77	226	94	123	175	92	196	109	153	283
9	61	139	228	40	257	106	124	198	70	227	121	154	168	85	197	281
11	35	249	60	149	232	65	219	105	134	202	80	189	120	164	172	279
13	150	239	37	245	54	135	209	67	215	99	165	179	82	185	114	277
273	247	50	144	240	44	217	95	129	210	74	187	110	159	180	89	17
271	234	45	254	52	140	204	75	224	97	125	174	90	194	112	155	19
269	59	142	230	39	255	104	127	200	69	225	119	157	170	84	195	21
267	36	251	58	147	233	66	221	103	132	203	81	191	118	162	173	23
265	148	237	38	246	56	133	207	68	216	101	163	177	83	186	116	25
263	248	51	146	238	42	218	96	131	208	72	188	111	161	178	87	27
261	236	43	252	53	141	206	73	222	98	126	176	88	192	113	156	29
259	57	143	231	41	253	102	128	201	71	223	117	158	171	86	193	31
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 10. *The block-bordered magic square of order 17 is written in two different ways by use of block-wise magic square of order 15. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 15, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 15, where blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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11 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 18

In this section, we shall present two different ways of writing magic square of order 18. One is with 36 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. The second is with 9 blocks of magic squares of order 6 of equal magic sums.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 18 is given by

$$S_{18 \times 18} := \frac{18 \times (1 + 18^2)}{2} = 2925.$$

We can write, $18 := 2 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 6. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 2925 by 6 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{2925}{6} = 487.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 3;} \\ (ii) \quad \frac{2925}{3} = 975 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 6.}$$

11.1 36 Blocks of Order 3

Example 11.1. *By the applications of Examples 2.1 and 2.4, we get a magic square of order 18 given by*

						2925
60	582	735	897	420	231	2925
744	222	906	393	564	96	2925
267	105	384	726	870	573	2925
879	411	87	591	249	708	2925
546	888	258	78	753	402	2925
429	717	555	240	69	915	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

11.2 9 Blocks of Order 6

Example 11.3. *9 blocks of magic squares of order 6 constructed according to Example 2.4 lead us to a magic square of order 18 given by*

Result 11. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 18 are as follows*

1. 36 Blocks of order 3: *The magic square of order 18 is constructed with 36 blocks of different magic square sums of order 3.*

Magic square sums of order 3, again lead us to a magic square of order 6;

2. 9 Blocks of order 6: *The magic square of order 18 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 6*

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12 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 19

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 is constructed in two different ways. These are based on **block-wise** magic squares of order 15 given in Examples 8.1 and 8.2.

12.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 15

Result 12. *The block-bordered magic square of order 19 is written in two different ways by use of block-wise magic square of order 15. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 15, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 15, where blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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13 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 20

In this section, we shall present three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 20. The first as magic square formed by 25 blocks of equal magic sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The second as magic square formed by 16 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 with different magic sums. The third as 4 blocks of equal sums of magic squares of order 10. In the first two cases, the magic squares are **pandiagonals**, while in the third case is just a magic square of order 20.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 20 is given by

$$S_{20 \times 20} := \frac{20 \times (1 + 20^2)}{2} = 4010.$$

We can write, $20 := 2 \times 2 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 5 and 10. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 4010 by 5, 4 and 2:

- (i) $\frac{4010}{5} = 802 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{4010}{4} = 1002.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (iii) $\frac{4010}{2} = 2005 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10.

Result 13. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 20 are as follows:*

1. **25 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandiagonal magic square of order 20 is constructed with equal pandiagonal magic squares sums of order 4.*
2. **16 Blocks of Order 5:** *The pandiagonal magic square of order 20 is constructed with different magic sums of pandiagonal magic squares of order 5. The 16 magic squares of order 5, lead us to a pandiagonal magic square of order 4;*
3. **4 Blocks of Order 10:** *The magic square of order 20 is constructed with equal sums magic squares of order 10.*

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14 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 21

In this section, we shall present two different ways of writing **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 21. The first as magic square formed by 49 blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 with equal magic sums. The second as 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7 with equal magic sums.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 21 is given by

$$S_{21 \times 21} := \frac{21 \times (1 + 21^2)}{2} = 4641.$$

We can write, $21 := 3 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 7. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 4641 by 7 and 3:

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & \frac{4641}{7} = 663 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3;} \\ (ii) \quad & \frac{4641}{3} = 1547 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 7.} \end{aligned}$$

14.1 49 Blocks of Order 3

Example 14.1. *A pandiagonal magic square of order 21 formed by 49 blocks of semi-magic squares of order 3 constructed according to Examples 2.1 and 2.5 is given by*

Result 14. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 21 are as follows:*

- 1. 49 Blocks of Order 3: The pandigonal magic square of order 21 is constructed with 49 blocks of equal sums semi-magic square (rows and columns) of order 3;*
- 2. 9 Blocks of Order 7: The pandigonal magic square of order 21 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 7.*

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15 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 22

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 is constructed in 6 different ways. These are based on **block-wise** magic squares of order 20, 18 and 16 given in Examples 13.1, 13.2, 13.4, 11.1, 11.3 and 9.2. The Example 9.1 is not considered as it is already included in Example 13.1.

15.1 Blocks of Order 4: Magic Square of Order 20

21	473	13	471	15	469	17	467	19	465	1	474	23	461	25	459	27	457	29	455	31	463
33	43	219	114	426	378	130	351	195	282	287	44	220	113	425	377	129	352	196	281	288	452
451	194	106	298	367	142	439	203	270	51	355	193	105	297	368	141	440	204	269	52	356	34
35	286	278	127	222	434	55	199	363	350	111	285	277	128	221	433	56	200	364	349	112	450
449	122	375	271	190	343	207	438	46	294	139	121	376	272	189	344	208	437	45	293	140	36
37	430	123	59	275	211	346	374	302	107	198	429	124	60	276	212	345	373	301	108	197	448
447	371	290	183	359	115	274	62	427	138	206	372	289	184	360	116	273	61	428	137	205	38
39	218	47	362	134	266	191	295	119	423	370	217	48	361	133	265	192	296	120	424	369	446
445	135	431	210	103	299	382	267	358	186	54	136	432	209	104	300	381	268	357	185	53	40
41	347	202	435	291	50	118	126	214	379	263	348	201	436	292	49	117	125	213	380	264	444
443	279	354	366	58	187	283	110	131	215	442	280	353	365	57	188	284	109	132	216	441	42
453	63	239	94	406	398	150	331	175	262	307	64	240	93	405	397	149	332	176	261	308	32
475	174	86	318	387	162	419	223	250	71	335	173	85	317	388	161	420	224	249	72	336	10
9	306	258	147	242	414	75	179	383	330	91	305	257	148	241	413	76	180	384	329	92	476
477	102	395	251	170	323	227	418	66	314	159	101	396	252	169	324	228	417	65	313	160	8
7	410	143	79	255	231	326	394	322	87	178	409	144	80	256	232	325	393	321	88	177	478
479	391	310	163	339	95	254	82	407	158	226	392	309	164	340	96	253	81	408	157	225	6
5	238	67	342	154	246	171	315	99	403	390	237	68	341	153	245	172	316	100	404	389	480
481	155	411	230	83	319	402	247	338	166	74	156	412	229	84	320	401	248	337	165	73	4
3	327	182	415	311	70	98	146	234	399	243	328	181	416	312	69	97	145	233	400	244	482
483	259	334	386	78	167	303	90	151	235	422	260	333	385	77	168	304	89	152	236	421	2
22	12	472	14	470	16	468	18	466	20	484	11	462	24	460	26	458	28	456	30	454	464

15.4 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 18

Example 15.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 22 with inner part as magic square of order 18 with blocks of order 3 is given by*

Result 15. *The block-bordered magic square of order 22 is written in six different ways by use of block-wise magic squares of orders 20, 18 and 16. In case of order 16, the idea of bimagic square of order 16 is considered. The block-wise details are as follows:*

- 1. Pandiagonal magic square of order 20, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
- 2. Pandiagonal magic square of order 20, where blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums;*
- 3. Magic square of order 20, where blocks order 10 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
- 4. Magic square of order 18, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sum;*
- 5. Magic square of order 18, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
- 6. Bimagic square of order 16, where blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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16 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 23

The block-bordered magic square of order 23 is constructed in 2 different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of order 21 given in Examples 14.1 and 14.2.

16.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 21

Example 16.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 23 with inner part as magic square of order 21 with blocks of order 3 is given by*

Result 16. The *block-bordered* magic square of order 23 is written in *two* different ways by use of *block-wise* magic squares of order 21. The *block-wise* details are as follows:

1. The *pandiagonal* magic square of 21, where the blocks of order 3 are of equal sums *semi-magic* squares
2. The *pandiagonal* magic square of 21, where the blocks of order 7 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with equal magic sums.

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17 Block-Wise Magic and Semi-Bimagic Squares of Order 24

In this section, we shall present three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 24. The first as magic square formed by 64 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. The second as magic square formed by 36 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. The third as 16 blocks of magic squares of order 6 with equal sums. In the first two cases, the magic squares of order 24 are **pandiagonal** magic squares, while in the third case it is just a magic square.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 24 is given by

$$S_{24 \times 24} := \frac{24 \times (1 + 24^2)}{2} = 6924.$$

We can write, $24 := 2^3 \times 3 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 8 and 12. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 6924 by 8, 6, 4, 3 and 2:

- (i) $\frac{6924}{8} = 865.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{6924}{6} = 1154 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{6924}{4} = 1731 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iv) $\frac{6924}{3} = 2308 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (v) $\frac{6924}{2} = 3462 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12.

In this case, the magic square is formed by 9 blocks of magic squares of order 8 with equal magic sums $S_{8 \times 8} := 2308$. Out of 9 blocks of order 8, three of them are **bimagic** squares with different **bimagic** sums, and the other 6 are **semi-bimagic** (**bimagic** only in rows and columns) resulting in a **semi-bimagic** square of order 24 (**bimagic** only in rows and columns), with **semi-bimagic** sums are $Sb1_{24 \times 24} := 2661124$ (rows and columns), $Sb2_{24 \times 24} := 2654292$ (upper diagonal) and $Sb3_{24 \times 24} := 2714116$ (lower diagonal).

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 17. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 24 are as follows:*

- 1. 64 Blocks of Order 3: Semi-Bimagic The pandiagonal magic square of order 24 is constructed with 64 blocks of different magic sums of magic squares of order 3. It is also semi-bimagic square of order 24;*
- 2. 36 Blocks of Order 4: The pandiagonal magic square of order 24 is constructed with 36 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4;*
- 3. 16 Blocks of Order 6: The magic square of order 24 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 6;*
- 4. 9 Blocks of Order 8: Semi-Bimagic The semi-bimagic square of order 24 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 8. Blocks of order 8 are either bimagic or semi-bimagic squares;*
- 5. 4 Blocks of Order 12: The magic squares of order 12 are constructed according to Result 5.1. This possibility comes under the first or second case described above, i.e., 4 blocks of order 12 with equal magic square sums lead us to a magic square of order 24.*

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18 Block-Wise Bimagic Square of Order 25

In this section, we shall present a **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 25 with 25 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The magic square is also **bimagic**.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 25 is given by

$$S_{25 \times 25} := \frac{25 \times (1 + 25^2)}{2} = 7825.$$

In this case, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 25 is also a **bimagic** with magic and **bimagic** sums, $S_{25 \times 25} := 7825$ and $Sb_{25 \times 25} := 3263025$ respectively. Each block of order 5 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with equal magic sums, $S_{5 \times 5} := 1565$. Details of this **bimagic** square can be seen in author's work [21].

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 18. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 25 is as follows:*

1. 25 blocks of order 5: Bimagic Square of Order 25 In this case, pandiagonal bimagic magic square of order 25 is constructed with 25 blocks of pandiagonal equal magic sums of order 5;

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19 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 26

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 is constructed in 4 different ways. These are based on **block-wise** magic squares of order 24 given in Examples 17.1, 17.2, 17.3 and 17.4.

19.1 Blocks of order 3: Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 24

Example 19.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 26 with inner part as magic square of order 24 with blocks of order 3 is given by*

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	267	482	51	554	268	481	52	553	269	480	53	552	270	479	54	551	271	478	55	550	272	477	56	549	638
637	122	483	338	411	121	484	337	412	120	485	336	413	119	486	335	414	118	487	334	415	117	488	333	416	40
41	626	123	410	195	625	124	409	196	624	125	408	197	623	126	407	198	622	127	406	199	621	128	405	200	636
635	339	266	555	194	340	265	556	193	341	264	557	192	342	263	558	191	343	262	559	190	344	261	560	189	42
43	273	476	57	548	274	475	58	547	275	474	59	546	276	473	60	545	277	472	61	544	278	471	62	543	634
633	116	489	332	417	115	490	331	418	114	491	330	419	113	492	329	420	112	493	328	421	111	494	327	422	44
45	620	129	404	201	619	130	403	202	618	131	402	203	617	132	401	204	616	133	400	205	615	134	399	206	632
631	345	260	561	188	346	259	562	187	347	258	563	186	348	257	564	185	349	256	565	184	350	255	566	183	46
47	279	470	63	542	280	469	64	541	281	468	65	540	282	467	66	539	283	466	67	538	284	465	68	537	630
629	110	495	326	423	109	496	325	424	108	497	324	425	107	498	323	426	106	499	322	427	105	500	321	428	48
49	614	135	398	207	613	136	397	208	612	137	396	209	611	138	395	210	610	139	394	211	609	140	393	212	628
627	351	254	567	182	352	253	568	181	353	252	569	180	354	251	570	179	355	250	571	178	356	249	572	177	50
639	285	464	69	536	286	463	70	535	287	462	71	534	288	461	72	533	289	460	73	532	290	459	74	531	38
665	104	501	320	429	103	502	319	430	102	503	318	431	101	504	317	432	100	505	316	433	99	506	315	434	12
11	608	141	392	213	607	142	391	214	606	143	390	215	605	144	389	216	604	145	388	217	603	146	387	218	666
667	357	248	573	176	358	247	574	175	359	246	575	174	360	245	576	173	361	244	577	172	362	243	578	171	10
9	291	458	75	530	292	457	76	529	293	456	77	528	294	455	78	527	295	454	79	526	296	453	80	525	668
669	98	507	314	435	97	508	313	436	96	509	312	437	95	510	311	438	94	511	310	439	93	512	309	440	8
7	602	147	386	219	601	148	385	220	600	149	384	221	599	150	383	222	598	151	382	223	597	152	381	224	670
671	363	242	579	170	364	241	580	169	365	240	581	168	366	239	582	167	367	238	583	166	368	237	584	165	6
5	297	452	81	524	298	451	82	523	299	450	83	522	300	449	84	521	301	448	85	520	302	447	86	519	672
673	92	513	308	441	91	514	307	442	90	515	306	443	89	516	305	444	88	517	304	445	87	518	303	446	4
3	596	153	380	225	595	154	379	226	594	155	378	227	593	156	377	228	592	157	376	229	591	158	375	230	674
675	369	236	585	164	370	235	586	163	371	234	587	162	372	233	588	161	373	232	589	160	374	231	590	159	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

19.3 Blocks of order 6: Magic Square of Order 24

Example 19.3. The block-bordered magic square of order 26 with inner part as magic square of order 24 with blocks of order 6 is given by

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	51	595	594	563	82	146	52	596	593	564	81	145	53	597	592	565	80	144	54	598	591	566	79	143	638
637	530	178	498	179	211	435	529	177	497	180	212	436	528	176	496	181	213	437	527	175	495	182	214	438	40
41	434	403	275	306	370	243	433	404	276	305	369	244	432	405	277	304	368	245	431	406	278	303	367	246	636
635	338	274	371	402	307	339	337	273	372	401	308	340	336	272	373	400	309	341	335	271	374	399	310	342	42
43	147	466	210	467	499	242	148	465	209	468	500	241	149	464	208	469	501	240	150	463	207	470	502	239	634
633	531	115	83	114	562	626	532	116	84	113	561	625	533	117	85	112	560	624	534	118	86	111	559	623	44
45	55	599	590	567	78	142	56	600	589	568	77	141	57	601	588	569	76	140	58	602	587	570	75	139	632
631	526	174	494	183	215	439	525	173	493	184	216	440	524	172	492	185	217	441	523	171	491	186	218	442	46
47	430	407	279	302	366	247	429	408	280	301	365	248	428	409	281	300	364	249	427	410	282	299	363	250	630
629	334	270	375	398	311	343	333	269	376	397	312	344	332	268	377	396	313	345	331	267	378	395	314	346	48
49	151	462	206	471	503	238	152	461	205	472	504	237	153	460	204	473	505	236	154	459	203	474	506	235	628
627	535	119	87	110	558	622	536	120	88	109	557	621	537	121	89	108	556	620	538	122	90	107	555	619	50
639	59	603	586	571	74	138	60	604	585	572	73	137	61	605	584	573	72	136	62	606	583	574	71	135	38
665	522	170	490	187	219	443	521	169	489	188	220	444	520	168	488	189	221	445	519	167	487	190	222	446	12
11	426	411	283	298	362	251	425	412	284	297	361	252	424	413	285	296	360	253	423	414	286	295	359	254	666
667	330	266	379	394	315	347	329	265	380	393	316	348	328	264	381	392	317	349	327	263	382	391	318	350	10
9	155	458	202	475	507	234	156	457	201	476	508	233	157	456	200	477	509	232	158	455	199	478	510	231	668
669	539	123	91	106	554	618	540	124	92	105	553	617	541	125	93	104	552	616	542	126	94	103	551	615	8
7	63	607	582	575	70	134	64	608	581	576	69	133	65	609	580	577	68	132	66	610	579	578	67	131	670
671	518	166	486	191	223	447	517	165	485	192	224	448	516	164	484	193	225	449	515	163	483	194	226	450	6
5	422	415	287	294	358	255	421	416	288	293	357	256	420	417	289	292	356	257	419	418	290	291	355	258	672
673	326	262	383	390	319	351	325	261	384	389	320	352	324	260	385	388	321	353	323	259	386	387	322	354	4
3	159	454	198	479	511	230	160	453	197	480	512	229	161	452	196	481	513	228	162	451	195	482	514	227	674
675	543	127	95	102	550	614	544	128	96	101	549	613	545	129	97	100	548	612	546	130	98	99	547	611	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

19.4 Blocks of order 8: Semi-Bimagic Square of Order 24

Example 19.4. *The block-bordered magic square of order 26 with inner part as magic square of order 24 with blocks of order 8 is given by*

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	193	460	349	64	322	619	502	199	144	413	396	113	275	570	551	246	170	435	374	87	297	596	525	224	638
637	319	622	499	202	184	469	340	73	270	575	546	251	137	420	389	120	296	597	524	225	159	446	363	98	40
41	52	361	472	181	211	490	607	334	101	408	425	132	258	539	558	287	75	386	447	158	236	513	584	309	636
635	214	487	610	331	61	352	481	172	263	534	563	282	108	401	432	125	237	512	585	308	86	375	458	147	42
43	355	58	175	478	484	217	328	613	402	107	126	431	533	264	281	564	380	81	152	453	507	242	303	590	634
633	493	208	337	604	358	55	178	475	540	257	288	557	407	102	131	426	518	231	314	579	381	80	153	452	44
45	466	187	70	343	625	316	205	496	419	138	119	390	576	269	252	545	441	164	93	368	602	291	230	519	632
631	616	325	196	505	463	190	67	346	569	276	245	552	414	143	114	395	591	302	219	530	440	165	92	369	46
47	146	411	398	111	273	572	549	248	169	436	373	88	298	595	526	223	192	461	348	65	323	618	503	198	630
629	272	573	548	249	135	422	387	122	295	598	523	226	160	445	364	97	318	623	498	203	185	468	341	72	48
49	99	410	423	134	260	537	560	285	76	385	448	157	235	514	583	310	53	360	473	180	210	491	606	335	628
627	261	536	561	284	110	399	434	123	238	511	586	307	85	376	457	148	215	486	611	330	60	353	480	173	50
639	404	105	128	429	531	266	279	566	379	82	151	454	508	241	304	589	354	59	174	479	485	216	329	612	38
665	542	255	290	555	405	104	129	428	517	232	313	580	382	79	154	451	492	209	336	605	359	54	179	474	12
11	417	140	117	392	578	267	254	543	442	163	94	367	601	292	229	520	467	186	71	342	624	317	204	497	666
667	567	278	243	554	416	141	116	393	592	301	220	529	439	166	91	370	617	324	197	504	462	191	66	347	10
9	168	437	372	89	299	594	527	222	194	459	350	63	321	620	501	200	145	412	397	112	274	571	550	247	668
669	294	599	522	227	161	444	365	96	320	621	500	201	183	470	339	74	271	574	547	250	136	421	388	121	8
7	77	384	449	156	234	515	582	311	51	362	471	182	212	489	608	333	100	409	424	133	259	538	559	286	670
671	239	510	587	306	84	377	456	149	213	488	609	332	62	351	482	171	262	535	562	283	109	400	433	124	6
5	378	83	150	455	509	240	305	588	356	57	176	477	483	218	327	614	403	106	127	430	532	265	280	565	672
673	516	233	312	581	383	78	155	450	494	207	338	603	357	56	177	476	541	256	289	556	406	103	130	427	4
3	443	162	95	366	600	293	228	521	465	188	69	344	626	315	206	495	418	139	118	391	577	268	253	544	674
675	593	300	221	528	438	167	90	371	615	326	195	506	464	189	68	345	568	277	244	553	415	142	115	394	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

19.5 Blocks of order 12: Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 24

Example 19.5. The *block-bordered* magic square of order 26 with inner part as magic square of order 24 with blocks of order 12 is given by

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	255	235	330	434	454	359	123	151	54	542	514	611	256	236	329	433	453	360	124	152	53	541	513	612	638
637	331	258	231	358	431	458	55	126	147	610	539	518	332	257	232	357	432	457	56	125	148	609	540	517	40
41	234	327	259	455	362	430	150	51	127	515	614	538	233	328	260	456	361	429	149	52	128	516	613	537	636
635	134	154	59	531	511	606	266	238	335	423	451	354	133	153	60	532	512	605	265	237	336	424	452	353	42
43	58	131	158	607	534	507	334	263	242	355	426	447	57	132	157	608	533	508	333	264	241	356	425	448	634
633	155	62	130	510	603	535	239	338	262	450	351	427	156	61	129	509	604	536	240	337	261	449	352	428	44
45	554	526	623	135	163	66	422	442	347	243	223	318	553	525	624	136	164	65	421	441	348	244	224	317	632
631	622	551	530	67	138	159	346	419	446	319	246	219	621	552	529	68	137	160	345	420	445	320	245	220	46
47	527	626	550	162	63	139	443	350	418	222	315	247	528	625	549	161	64	140	444	349	417	221	316	248	630
629	411	439	342	254	226	323	543	523	618	146	166	71	412	440	341	253	225	324	544	524	617	145	165	72	48
49	343	414	435	322	251	230	619	546	519	70	143	170	344	413	436	321	252	229	620	545	520	69	144	169	628
627	438	339	415	227	326	250	522	615	547	167	74	142	437	340	416	228	325	249	521	616	548	168	73	141	50
639	279	211	306	410	478	383	99	175	78	566	490	587	280	212	305	409	477	384	100	176	77	565	489	588	38
665	307	282	207	382	407	482	79	102	171	586	563	494	308	281	208	381	408	481	80	101	172	585	564	493	12
11	210	303	283	479	386	406	174	75	103	491	590	562	209	304	284	480	385	405	173	76	104	492	589	561	666
667	110	178	83	555	487	582	290	214	311	399	475	378	109	177	84	556	488	581	289	213	312	400	476	377	10
9	82	107	182	583	558	483	310	287	218	379	402	471	81	108	181	584	557	484	309	288	217	380	401	472	668
669	179	86	106	486	579	559	215	314	286	474	375	403	180	85	105	485	580	560	216	313	285	473	376	404	8
7	578	502	599	111	187	90	398	466	371	267	199	294	577	501	600	112	188	89	397	465	372	268	200	293	670
671	598	575	506	91	114	183	370	395	470	295	270	195	597	576	505	92	113	184	369	396	469	296	269	196	6
5	503	602	574	186	87	115	467	374	394	198	291	271	504	601	573	185	88	116	468	373	393	197	292	272	672
673	387	463	366	278	202	299	567	499	594	122	190	95	388	464	365	277	201	300	568	500	593	121	189	96	4
3	367	390	459	298	275	206	595	570	495	94	119	194	368	389	460	297	276	205	596	569	496	93	120	193	674
675	462	363	391	203	302	274	498	591	571	191	98	118	461	364	392	204	301	273	497	592	572	192	97	117	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

Result 19. *The block-bordered magic square of order 26 is written in four different ways by use of block-wise magic square of order 24. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 24, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums. These blocks of order 3 results in a semi-bimagic square of order 24.*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 24, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
3. *Magic square of order 24, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
4. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 24, where block of order 8 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums. Moreover, blocks of order 8 are either bimagic squares or semi-bimagic squares with different bimagic or semi-bimagic sums. These blocks of order 8 results in a semi-bimagic square of order 24.*

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20 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 27

In this section, we shall present three different ways of writing **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 27. The first as magic square formed by 81 blocks of equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. The second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 9. The third as 9 blocks of **bimagic** squares of order 9 resulting a magic square of order 27.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 27 is given by

$$S_{27 \times 27} := \frac{27 \times (1 + 27^2)}{2} = 9855.$$

We can write, $27 := 3^3 = 3 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 9. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 9855 by 9 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{9855}{9} = 1095 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{9855}{3} = 3285 \implies$ equal blocks of order 9.

In this case, the magic sums is $S_{27 \times 27} := 9855$. All the 9 blocks of order 9 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of equal magic sums, $S_{9 \times 9} := 3285$. Moreover, the sum of nine members of each block of order 3 are same as of magic square sums of order 9, i.e., $S_{3 \times (9)} := 3285$. The construction of this magic square is due to Dwane [5].

Summarizing, we have the following result:

Result 20. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 27 are as follows:*

1. *81 Blocks of Order 3: The pandigonal magic square of order 27 is constructed with 81 blocks of equal semi-magic square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
2. *9 Blocks of Order 9: The pandigonal magic square of order 27 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic square of order 9. Moreover, sums nine members of each block of order 3 is the same as of magic square of order 9.*

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21 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 28

In this section, we shall present three different ways of writing **pandiagonal** magic square of order 28. The first as magic square formed by 49 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. The second as magic square formed by 16 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7. The third as magic square formed by 4 blocks of equal magic sums of order 14. In the first two cases the magic squares of order 28 are **pandiagonal**, while in the third case, it is just a magic square.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 28 is given by

$$S_{28 \times 28} := \frac{28 \times (1 + 28^2)}{2} = 10990.$$

We can write, $28 := 2^2 \times 7 = 2 \times 2 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 7 and 14. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 10990 by 7, 4 and 2:

- (i) $\frac{10990}{7} = 1570 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{10990}{4} = 2745.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 7;
- (iii) $\frac{10990}{2} = 5495 \implies$ equal blocks of order 14.

Result 21. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 28 are as follows:*

- 1. 49 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 28 is constructed with 49 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4.*
- 2. 16 Blocks of Order 7:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 28 is constructed with 16 blocks of different magic sums of pandiagonal magic squares of order 7. Also, magic sums of order 7 results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 4.*
- 3. 4 Blocks of Order 14:** *The magic square of order 28 is constructed with 4 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 14.*

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22 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 29

The block-bordered magic square of order 29 is constructed in 3 different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of order 27 given in Examples 20.1, 20.2 and 18.1

22.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 27

Example 22.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 29 with inner part as magic square of order 27 with blocks of order 3 is given by*

814	786	788	790	792	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	27	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	812
55	678	505	80	692	490	81	682	507	74	693	494	76	698	495	70	699	500	64	686	511	66	703	501	59	688	515	60	787
53	73	701	489	58	702	503	75	695	493	62	697	504	63	691	509	68	685	510	79	687	497	69	680	514	83	681	499	789
51	512	57	694	513	71	679	506	61	696	508	72	683	502	77	684	496	78	689	498	65	700	491	82	690	492	67	704	791
49	705	100	458	719	85	459	709	102	452	720	89	454	725	90	448	726	95	442	713	106	444	730	96	437	715	110	438	793
47	451	728	84	436	729	98	453	722	88	440	724	99	441	718	104	446	712	105	457	714	92	447	707	109	461	708	94	795
45	107	435	721	108	449	706	101	439	723	103	450	710	97	455	711	91	456	716	93	443	727	86	460	717	87	445	731	797
43	516	559	188	530	544	189	520	561	182	531	548	184	536	549	178	537	554	172	524	565	174	541	555	167	526	569	168	799
41	181	539	543	166	540	557	183	533	547	170	535	558	171	529	563	176	523	564	187	525	551	177	518	568	191	519	553	801
39	566	165	532	567	179	517	560	169	534	562	180	521	556	185	522	550	186	527	552	173	538	545	190	528	546	175	542	803
37	570	208	485	584	193	486	574	210	479	585	197	481	590	198	475	591	203	469	578	214	471	595	204	464	580	218	465	805
35	478	593	192	463	594	206	480	587	196	467	589	207	468	583	212	473	577	213	484	579	200	474	572	217	488	573	202	807
33	215	462	586	216	476	571	209	466	588	211	477	575	205	482	576	199	483	581	201	470	592	194	487	582	195	472	596	809
31	408	235	620	422	220	621	412	237	614	423	224	616	428	225	610	429	230	604	416	241	606	433	231	599	418	245	600	811
29	613	431	219	598	432	233	615	425	223	602	427	234	603	421	239	608	415	240	619	417	227	609	410	244	623	411	229	813
817	242	597	424	243	611	409	236	601	426	238	612	413	232	617	414	226	618	419	228	605	430	221	622	420	222	607	434	25
819	246	370	647	260	355	648	250	372	641	261	359	643	266	360	637	267	365	631	254	376	633	271	366	626	256	380	627	23
821	640	269	354	625	270	368	642	263	358	629	265	369	630	259	374	635	253	375	646	255	362	636	248	379	650	249	364	21
823	377	624	262	378	638	247	371	628	264	373	639	251	367	644	252	361	645	257	363	632	268	356	649	258	357	634	272	19
825	300	667	296	314	652	297	304	669	290	315	656	292	320	657	286	321	662	280	308	673	282	325	663	275	310	677	276	17
827	289	323	651	274	324	665	291	317	655	278	319	666	279	313	671	284	307	672	295	309	659	285	302	676	299	303	661	15
829	674	273	316	675	287	301	668	277	318	670	288	305	664	293	306	658	294	311	660	281	322	653	298	312	654	283	326	13
831	111	397	755	125	382	756	115	399	749	126	386	751	131	387	745	132	392	739	119	403	741	136	393	734	121	407	735	11
833	748	134	381	733	135	395	750	128	385	737	130	396	738	124	401	743	118	402	754	120	389	744	113	406	758	114	391	9
835	404	732	127	405	746	112	398	736	129	400	747	116	394	752	117	388	753	122	390	740	133	383	757	123	384	742	137	7
837	138	775	350	152	760	351	142	777	344	153	764	346	158	765	340	159	770	334	146	781	336	163	771	329	148	785	330	5
839	343	161	759	328	162	773	345	155	763	332	157	774	333	151	779	338	145	780	349	147	767	339	140	784	353	141	769	3
841	782	327	154	783	341	139	776	331	156	778	342	143	772	347	144	766	348	149	768	335	160	761	352	150	762	337	164	1
30	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	815	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	28

22.2 Blocks of Order 9: Magic Square of Order 27

Example 22.2. *The block-bordered magic square of order 29 with inner part as magic square of order 27 with pandiagonal blocks of order 9 is given by*

814	786	788	790	792	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	27	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	812
55	57	679	491	73	695	504	80	699	511	66	688	500	82	704	513	62	681	493	75	697	509	64	686	495	71	690	502	787
53	191	729	379	168	709	359	175	716	363	173	711	361	177	718	368	184	725	372	182	720	370	186	727	377	166	707	354	789
51	286	584	393	293	588	400	279	577	389	295	593	402	275	570	382	288	586	398	277	575	384	284	579	391	297	595	407	791
49	408	220	599	424	236	612	431	240	619	417	229	608	433	245	621	413	222	601	426	238	617	415	227	603	422	231	610	793
47	542	108	649	519	88	629	526	95	633	524	90	631	528	97	638	535	104	642	533	99	640	537	106	647	517	86	624	795
45	313	206	744	320	210	751	306	199	740	322	215	753	302	192	733	315	208	749	304	197	735	311	201	742	324	217	758	797
43	759	328	140	775	344	153	782	348	160	768	337	149	784	353	162	764	330	142	777	346	158	766	335	144	773	339	151	799
41	569	459	271	546	439	251	553	446	255	551	441	253	555	448	260	562	455	264	560	450	262	564	457	269	544	437	246	801
39	664	476	123	671	480	130	657	469	119	673	485	132	653	462	112	666	478	128	655	467	114	662	471	121	675	487	137	803
37	381	274	572	397	290	585	404	294	592	390	283	581	406	299	594	386	276	574	399	292	590	388	281	576	395	285	583	805
35	515	81	703	492	61	683	499	68	687	497	63	685	501	70	692	508	77	696	506	72	694	510	79	701	490	59	678	807
33	367	179	717	374	183	724	360	172	713	376	188	726	356	165	706	369	181	722	358	170	708	365	174	715	378	190	731	809
31	732	301	194	748	317	207	755	321	214	741	310	203	757	326	216	737	303	196	750	319	212	739	308	198	746	312	205	811
29	623	432	244	600	412	224	607	419	228	605	414	226	609	421	233	616	428	237	614	423	235	618	430	242	598	410	219	813
817	637	530	96	644	534	103	630	523	92	646	539	105	626	516	85	639	532	101	628	521	87	635	525	94	648	541	110	25
819	111	652	464	127	668	477	134	672	484	120	661	473	136	677	486	116	654	466	129	670	482	118	659	468	125	663	475	23
821	164	783	352	141	763	332	148	770	336	146	765	334	150	772	341	157	779	345	155	774	343	159	781	350	139	761	327	21
823	259	557	447	266	561	454	252	550	443	268	566	456	248	543	436	261	559	452	250	548	438	257	552	445	270	568	461	19
825	705	355	167	721	371	180	728	375	187	714	364	176	730	380	189	710	357	169	723	373	185	712	362	171	719	366	178	17
827	596	405	298	573	385	278	580	392	282	578	387	280	582	394	287	589	401	291	587	396	289	591	403	296	571	383	273	15
829	691	503	69	698	507	76	684	496	65	700	512	78	680	489	58	693	505	74	682	494	60	689	498	67	702	514	83	13
831	84	625	518	100	641	531	107	645	538	93	634	527	109	650	540	89	627	520	102	643	536	91	632	522	98	636	529	11
833	218	756	325	195	736	305	202	743	309	200	738	307	204	745	314	211	752	318	209	747	316	213	754	323	193	734	300	9
835	232	611	420	239	615	427	225	604	416	241	620	429	221	597	409	234	613	425	223	602	411	230	606	418	243	622	434	7
837	435	247	545	451	263	558	458	267	565	444	256	554	460	272	567	440	249	547	453	265	563	442	254	549	449	258	556	5
839	488	135	676	465	115	656	472	122	660	470	117	658	474	124	665	481	131	669	479	126	667	483	133	674	463	113	651	3
841	340	152	771	347	156	778	333	145	767	349	161	780	329	138	760	342	154	776	331	143	762	338	147	769	351	163	785	1
30	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	815	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	28

22.3 Blocks of Order 5: Bimagic Square of Order 25

Example 22.3. The block-bordered magic square of order 29 with inner part as magic square of order 25 with blocks of order 5 is given by

814	786	788	790	792	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	27	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	812
55	760	107	105	103	101	99	97	95	93	91	89	87	85	83	763	765	767	769	771	773	775	777	779	781	783	785	84	787
53	734	109	277	415	583	721	551	689	232	245	388	343	381	519	662	200	655	173	311	474	492	447	585	628	141	304	108	789
51	736	565	733	121	259	427	257	395	538	701	214	669	187	350	368	531	461	499	642	180	323	153	291	454	597	610	106	791
49	738	271	409	577	715	133	688	226	239	407	545	375	518	681	194	337	167	330	473	486	649	604	622	135	303	441	104	793
47	740	727	115	283	421	559	389	557	695	213	251	206	344	362	525	668	498	636	174	317	480	285	453	591	629	147	102	795
45	742	433	571	709	127	265	220	238	401	539	707	512	675	193	356	369	324	467	505	648	161	616	154	297	435	603	100	797
43	744	643	181	319	462	500	455	598	611	149	292	122	260	428	566	729	534	702	215	258	396	351	364	532	670	188	98	799
41	746	469	487	650	168	331	136	299	442	605	623	578	716	129	272	410	240	408	546	684	227	682	195	338	376	514	96	801
39	748	175	318	481	494	637	592	630	148	286	449	279	422	560	728	116	696	209	252	390	558	363	526	664	207	345	94	803
37	750	506	644	162	325	468	298	436	599	617	155	710	128	266	429	572	402	540	708	221	234	189	357	370	513	676	92	805
35	752	312	475	493	656	169	624	142	305	448	586	416	579	722	110	278	233	246	384	552	690	520	663	201	339	382	90	807
33	754	547	685	228	241	404	334	377	515	683	196	651	164	332	470	488	443	606	619	137	300	130	273	411	574	717	88	809
31	756	253	391	554	697	210	665	208	346	359	527	482	495	638	176	314	144	287	450	593	631	561	724	117	280	423	86	811
29	81	704	222	235	403	541	371	509	677	190	358	163	326	464	507	645	600	618	156	294	437	267	430	573	711	124	761	813
817	80	385	553	691	229	247	202	340	383	521	659	489	657	170	313	476	306	444	587	625	143	723	111	274	417	580	762	25
819	78	216	254	397	535	703	533	671	184	352	365	320	463	501	639	182	612	150	293	456	594	424	567	730	123	261	764	23
821	76	451	589	632	145	288	118	281	419	562	725	555	698	211	249	392	347	360	528	666	204	634	177	315	483	496	766	21
823	74	157	295	438	601	614	569	712	125	268	431	236	399	542	705	223	678	191	354	372	510	465	508	646	159	327	768	19
825	72	588	626	139	307	445	275	418	581	719	112	692	230	248	386	549	379	522	660	203	341	171	309	477	490	658	770	17
827	70	289	457	595	613	151	731	119	262	425	568	398	536	699	217	255	185	353	366	529	672	502	640	183	321	459	772	15
829	68	620	138	301	439	607	412	575	718	131	269	224	242	405	548	686	516	679	197	335	378	333	471	484	652	165	774	13
831	66	355	373	511	674	192	647	160	328	466	504	434	602	615	158	296	126	264	432	570	713	543	706	219	237	400	776	11
833	64	661	199	342	380	523	478	491	654	172	310	140	308	446	584	627	582	720	113	276	414	244	387	550	693	231	778	9
835	62	367	530	673	186	349	179	322	460	503	641	596	609	152	290	458	263	426	564	732	120	700	218	256	394	537	780	7
837	60	198	336	374	517	680	485	653	166	329	472	302	440	608	621	134	714	132	270	413	576	406	544	687	225	243	782	5
839	58	524	667	205	348	361	316	479	497	635	178	633	146	284	452	590	420	563	726	114	282	212	250	393	556	694	784	3
841	758	735	737	739	741	743	745	747	749	751	753	755	757	759	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	65	63	61	59	57	82	1
30	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	815	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	28

Result 22. *The block-bordered magic square of order 29 is written in three different ways by use of block-wise magic squares of orders 27 and 25. In case of order 25, the idea of bimagic square of order 25 is considered. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 27, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 27, where blocks of order 9 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums.*
3. *Pandiagonal bimagic square of order 25, where blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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23 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 30

In this section, we shall present four different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 30. The first as magic square formed by 36 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5. The second as magic square formed by 25 blocks of magic squares of order 6. The third as magic square formed by 9 blocks of magic squares of order 10. The fourth way as magic square formed by 100 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 30 is given by

$$S_{30 \times 30} := \frac{30 \times (1 + 30^2)}{2} = 13515.$$

We can write, $30 := 2 \times 3 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 5, 6 and 10. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 13515 by 10, 6, 5 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{13515}{10} = 1351.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{13515}{6} = 2252.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (i) $\frac{13515}{5} = 2703 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (ii) $\frac{13515}{3} = 4505 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10.

23.1 100 Blocks of Order 3

Example 23.1. *A magic square of order 30 formed by 100 blocks of magic squares of order 3 constructed according to Example 2.1 is given by*

										13515
96	2598	1221	1725	429	2013	1482	2310	717	924	13515
2031	375	2589	1194	1527	978	2256	123	1752	690	13515
1185	1779	654	2337	951	420	2058	1446	2553	132	13515
1797	150	2022	933	636	2274	1239	2535	411	1518	13515
1473	906	1788	2040	1212	645	2571	447	114	2319	13515
2292	1203	366	708	2580	1491	177	1734	969	1995	13515
699	1464	987	141	2265	2562	1770	1248	1986	393	13515
960	672	2283	2526	168	1257	384	2049	1455	1761	13515
2544	2067	1500	402	1743	159	915	681	2328	1176	13515
438	2301	105	1509	2004	1716	663	942	1230	2607	13515
13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515

23.2 36 Blocks of Order 5

Example 23.3. A magic square of order 30 formed by 36 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5 constructed according to Example 2.3 is given by

						13515
2165	2275	2300	2330	2245	2200	13515
2305	2195	2335	2230	2265	2185	13515
2220	2190	2225	2295	2315	2270	13515
2320	2240	2180	2280	2210	2285	13515
2255	2325	2215	2175	2310	2235	13515
2250	2290	2260	2205	2170	2340	13515
13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515

23.3 25 Blocks of Order 6

Example 23.5. *A magic square of order 30 formed by 25 blocks of magic squares of order 6 constructed according to Example 2.4 is given by*

Result 23. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 30 are as follows:*

1. **100 Blocks of Order 3:** *The magic square of order 30 is constructed with 100 blocks of different magic sums of magic squares of order 3. Also 100 magic sums of order 3 results in a magic square of order 10;*
2. **36 Blocks of Order 5:** *The magic square of order 30 is constructed with 36 blocks of different magic sums of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5;*
3. **25 Blocks of Order 6:** *The magic square of order 30 is constructed with 25 blocks of equal sum magic squares of order 6;*
4. **9 Blocks of Order 10:** *The magic square of order 30 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sum magic squares of order 10;*

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24 Block-Boarded Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 31

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 is constructed in 3 different ways. These are based on **block-wise** magic squares of order 27 given in Examples 20.1, 20.2 and 18.1.

24.1 Blocks of Order 3: Pandiagonal Magic Square of order 27

Example 24.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 31 with inner part as pandiagonal magic square of order 27 with blocks of order 3 is given by*

Result 24. *The block-bordered magic square of order 29 is written in three different ways by use of block-wise magic squares of orders 27 and 25. In case of order 25, the idea of bimagic square of order 25 is considered. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 27, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 27, where blocks of order 9 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
3. *Pandiagonal bimagic square of order 25, where blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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25 Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 32

In this section, we shall present two ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 32. The first as magic square formed by 64 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Second as 16 blocks of **bimagic** squares of order 8 with equal magic sums resulting in **bimagic** square of order 32.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 32 is given by

$$S_{32 \times 32} := \frac{32 \times (1 + 32^2)}{2} = 16400.$$

We can write, $32 := 2^5 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4 and 8. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 16400 by 8 and 4:

$$(i) \quad \frac{16400}{8} = 2050 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;} \\ (ii) \quad \frac{16400}{4} = 4100 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 8.}$$

		11201200	11201200	11201200	11201200
	2808468	2775684	2857700	2759348	11201200
11201200	2857652	2759396	2808452	2775700	11201200
11201200	2759300	2857620	2775732	2808548	11201200
11201200	2775780	2808500	2759316	2857604	11201200
	11201200	11201200	11201200	11201200	11201200

Result 25. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 32 are as follows:*

1. **64 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandiagonal magic square of order 32 is constructed with 64 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4.*
2. **16 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic -** *The pandiagonal bimagic square of order 32 is constructed with 16 blocks of bimagic or semi-bimagic squares of order 8 with different sums. The 16 sums of bimagic or semi-bimagic squares of order 8 again lead us to a pandiagonal magic square of order 4.*

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26 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 33

In this section, we shall present two different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 33. The first as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 11 with equal magic sums. The second as 121 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with equal magic sums.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 33 is given by

$$S_{33 \times 33} := \frac{33 \times (1 + 33^2)}{2} = 17985.$$

We can write, $33 := 3 \times 11$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 11. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 17985 by 11 and 3:

Result 26. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 33 are as follows:*

- 1. 121 Blocks of Order 3: The pandigonal magic square of order 33 is constructed with 121 blocks of equal semi-magic square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
- 2. 9 Blocks of Order 11: The pandigonal magic square of order 33 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 11.*

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27 Block-Boarded Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 34

The block-bordered magic square of order 34 is constructed in 9 different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of order 32, 30 and 28 given in Examples 25.1, 25.2, 23.1, 23.3, 23.5, 23.6, 21.1, 21.2 and 21.4.

27.1 Blocks of Order 4: Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 32

Example 27.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 34 with inner part as pandiagonal magic square of order 32 with blocks of order 4 is given by*

Result 27. *The block-bordered magic square of order 34 is written in nine different ways by use of block-wise magic squares of orders 32, 30 and 28. In case of order 32, one of the possibility is with bimagic square of order 32. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 32, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal bimagic square of order 32, where blocks of order 8 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums. Also the magic squares of order 8 are either bimagic or semi-bimagic squares with different bimagic or semi-bimagic sums;*
3. *Magic square of order 30, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums;*
4. *Magic square of order 30, where blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums;*
5. *Magic square of order 30, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
6. *Magic square of order 30, where blocks of order 10 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
7. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 28, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
8. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 28, where blocks of order 7 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums;*
9. *Magic square of order 28, where blocks of order 14 are magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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28 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 35

In this section, we shall present two different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 35. The first as magic square formed by 49 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 with equal magic sums. The second as magic square formed by 25 blocks of

pandiagonal magic squares of order 7 with equal magic sums. In both the cases, the magic squares of order 35 are **pandiagonal**.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 35 is given by

$$S_{35 \times 35} := \frac{35 \times (1 + 35^2)}{2} = 21455.$$

We can write, $35 := 5 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 5 and 7. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 21455 by 7 and 5:

$$(i) \quad \frac{21455}{7} = 3065 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 5;} \\ (ii) \quad \frac{21455}{5} = 4291 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 7.}$$

28.1 49 Blocks of Order 5

Example 28.1. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 35 formed by 49 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5 constructed according to Example 2.3 is given by

Result 28. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 35 are as follows:*

1. **49 Blocks of Order 5:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 35 is constructed with equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 7;*
2. **25 Blocks of Order 7:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 35 is constructed with equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 5.*

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29 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 36

In this section, we shall present six different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 36. The first as magic square formed by 144 blocks of magic squares of order 3. The second as magic square formed by 81 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The third as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 12, where in each case there are 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3. The fourth as magic square formed by 36 blocks of magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums. The fifth as 16 blocks of **bimagic** squares of order 9. In the first four cases, the magic square of order 36 is **pandiagonal**, while in the fifth and sixth it is just a magic square of order 36.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 36 is given by

$$S_{36 \times 36} := \frac{36 \times (1 + 36^2)}{2} = 23346.$$

We can write, $36 := 2^2 \times 3^2 = 2 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 9 and 12. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 23346 by 12, 9, 6, 4 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{23346}{12} = 1945.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{23346}{9} = 2594 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{23346}{6} = 3891 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iii) $\frac{23346}{4} = 5836.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 9;
- (iv) $\frac{23346}{3} = 7782 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12.

29.1 144 Blocks of Order 3

We observe that in the Examples 29.4 and 29.5 that the 3×3 blocks are not magic squares of order 3. In Example 29.5, the 3×3 blocks are semi-magic squares in each block of order 9×9 . On the other side, it is impossible to have all the 3×3 blocks of equal sums as 23346 is not divisible by 12, i.e., $23346/12 := 1945.5$. Below is a example of a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 36 where each block of order 3 is a magic square giving total 144 blocks of magic squares of order 3:

Example 29.1. *A pandiagonal magic square of order 36 formed by 144 blocks of magic squares of order 3 constructed according to Example 2.1 is given by*

		23346	23346	23346	23346
	5823	5868	5769	5886	23346
23346	5778	5877	5832	5859	23346
23346	5904	5787	5850	5805	23346
23346	5841	5814	5895	5796	23346
	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346

29.5 9 Blocks of Order 12

Example 29.8. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 36 formed by 9 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 12 constructed according to Example 5.3 is given by

Result 29. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 36 are as follows:*

1. **144 Blocks of Order 3:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 36 is constructed with 144 blocks of different magic sums of magic squares of order 3. Also 144 magic sums of order 3 results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 12;*
2. **81 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 36 is constructed with 81 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4;*
3. **36 Blocks of Order 6:** *The magic square of order 36 is constructed with 36 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 6;*
4. **16 Blocks of Order 9:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 36 is constructed with 16 blocks of different pandiagonal magic squares sums of order 9. Also 16 magic sums of order 9 results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 4;*
5. **9 Blocks of Order 12:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 36 is constructed with 9 blocks of pandiagonal magic squares equal magic sums of order 12. The magic squares of order 12 are constructed according to part (i) of Result 5.1, i.e., different magic square sums of order 3.*

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30 Block-Boarded Magic Squares of Order 37

The block-bordered magic square of order 37 is constructed in four different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of orders 35 and 33 given in Examples 28.1, 28.2, 26.2 and 26.1.

30.1 Blocks of Order 5: Magic Square of Order 35

Example 30.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 34 with inner part as pandiagonal magic square of order 32 with blocks of order 4 is given by*

Result 30. *The block-bordered magic square of order 36 is written in four different ways by use of block-wise magic squares of orders 35 and 33. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 35, where the blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 35, where the blocks of order 7 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
3. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 33, where the blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
4. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 33, where the blocks of order 11 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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31 Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 38

The block-bordered magic squares of order 38 are constructed in two different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of order 36 given in Examples 29.1, 29.4, 29.5, 29.6 and 29.8.

31.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 36

Example 31.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 38 with inner part as pandiagonal magic square of order 36 with blocks of order 3 is given by*

Result 31. *The block-bordered magic square of order 38 is written in six different ways by use of block-wise magic squares of order 36. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
3. *Magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
4. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 9 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums. Moreover, blocks of order 9×9 is formed by semi-magic squares of order 3 with equal semi-magic sums;*
5. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 12 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums. Moreover, blocks of order 3×3 is semi-magic square with different semi-magic sums.*

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32 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 39

The **block-wise** construction of magic squares of order 39 depends on the product 3×13 , i.e., either we can construct it by blocks of order 3 or by blocks of order 13. The magic square sum of order 39 is given by

$$S_{39 \times 39} := \frac{39 \times (1 + 39^2)}{2} = 29679.$$

Let's see the division of 29679 by 13 and 3.

$$(i) \quad \frac{29679}{13} = 2293 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{29679}{3} = 9893 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 13.}$$

This implies that we can made **block-wise** construction of magic squares of order 39, where each blocks of orders 3 and 13 are of

Result 32. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 39 are as follows:*

1. **169 Blocks of Order 3:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 39 is constructed with 169 blocks of equal semi-magic square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
2. **9 Blocks of Order 13:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 39 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 13.*

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33 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 40

In this section, we shall present four different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 40. The first as magic square formed by 100 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. The second as magic square formed by 64 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 with different magic sums. The third as 25 blocks of **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic** squares of order 8 resulting in **bimagic** square of order 40. The forth as 16 blocks of order 10.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 40 is given by

$$S_{40 \times 40} := \frac{40 \times (1 + 40^2)}{2} = 32020.$$

We can write $40 = 2 \times 2 \times 5$. This means that we can have blocks of orders 4, 5, 8 and 10. Let's see below divisions of the 32020 by 10, 8, 5 and 4:

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & \frac{32020}{10} = 3202 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{equal blocks of order 4;} \\ (ii) \quad & \frac{32020}{8} = 4002.5 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{unequal blocks of order 5;} \\ (iii) \quad & \frac{32020}{5} = 6404 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{equal blocks of order 8;} \\ (iv) \quad & \frac{32020}{4} = 8005 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \text{equal blocks of order 10.} \end{aligned}$$

This implies that we can made **block-wise** construction of magic square of order 40 with equal magic sums blocks of orders 4, 8 and 10. In case of blocks of order 5, this construction shall be made by different magic sums. In case of blocks of order 8, the magic square constructed is **bimagic**, where each block of order 8 is either **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic**. In order to construct these magic squares we need magic squares of orders 4, 5, 8 and 10. These are given in examples below:

33.1 Blocks of Order 4

Example 33.1. *The pandiagonal magic square of order 40 with equal sum blocks of order 4 is given by*

Result 33. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 40 are as follows:*

- 1. 100 Blocks of Order 4: The pandigonal magic square of order 40 is constructed with 100 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4;*
- 2. 64 Blocks of Order 5: The pandigonal magic square of order 40 is constructed with 64 blocks of different pandiagonal magic squares sums of order 5;*
- 3. 25 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - The pandigonal bimagic square of order 40 is constructed with 25 blocks of bimagic or semi-bimagic pandiagonal magic squares of order 8;*
- 4. 16 Blocks of Order 10: The magic square of order 40 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 10.*

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34 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 41

The block-bordered magic square of order 41 is constructed in two different ways based on block-wise magic squares of order 39 given in Examples 32.1 and 32.2.

34.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 39

Example 34.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 41 with inner part as pandiagonal magic square of order 39 with blocks of order 3 is given by*

Result 34. *The block-bordered magic square of order 41 is written in two different ways by use of block-wise magic square of order 39. The block-wise details are as follows:*

- 1. Pandiagonal magic square of order 39, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
- 2. Pandiagonal magic square of order 39, where blocks of order 13 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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35 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 42

In this section, we shall present four different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 42. The first as 196 blocks of magic square order 3 with unequal sums. The second as 49 blocks of magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums. The third as 36 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7. The fourth as 9 blocks of magic squares of order 14.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 42 is given by

$$S_{42 \times 42} := \frac{42 \times (1 + 42^2)}{2} = 37065.$$

We can write $42 := 2 \times 3 \times 7$. Let's see below the division of the sum 37065 by 14, 7, 6 and 3:

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & \frac{37065}{14} = 2647.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 3;} \\ (ii) \quad & \frac{37065}{7} = 5295 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 6;} \\ (iii) \quad & \frac{37065}{6} = 6176.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 7;} \\ (iv) \quad & \frac{37065}{3} = 12355 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 14.} \end{aligned}$$

This implies that we can make **block-wise** construction of magic square of order 42 with equal magic sums blocks of order 6 and 14. In case of blocks of orders 3 and 7, the construction of magic squares of order 42 is with different magic sums. In order to construct

Result 35. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 42 are as follows:*

1. **196 Blocks of Order 3:** *The magic square of order 42 is constructed with 196 blocks of different magic squares sums of order 3. Also 196 magic sums of order 3 results in a magic square of order 14;*
 2. **49 Blocks of Order 6:** *The magic square of order 42 is constructed with 49 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 6.*
 3. **36 Blocks of Order 7:** *The magic square of order 42 is constructed with 36 blocks of different **pandiagonal** magic square sums of order 7.*
 4. **9 Blocks of Order 14:** *The magic square of order 42 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 14.*
- In this case, we don't have any **pandiagonal** magic square of order 42.*

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36 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 43

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 43 is constructed in two different ways based on **block-wise** magic squares of order 39 given in Examples 32.1 and 32.2.

36.1 Blocks of Order 3: Magic Square of Order 39

Example 36.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 43 with inner part as **pandiagonal** magic square of order 39 with blocks of order 3 is given by*

Result 36. *The block-bordered magic square of order 43 is written in two different ways by use of block-wise magic square of order 39. The block-wise details are as follows:*

- 1. Pandiagonal magic square of order 39, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
- 2. Pandiagonal magic square of order 39, where blocks of order 13 are pandiagonal magic square with equal magic sums.*

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37 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 44

In this section, we shall present three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 44. The first as 121 blocks of magic square order 4 of equal sums. The second as 16 blocks of magic squares of order 11 with different magic sums. The third as 4 blocks of magic squares of order 22.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 44 is given by

$$S_{44 \times 44} := \frac{44 \times (1 + 44^2)}{2} = 42614.$$

This sum is divisible by 11 and 2, but not by 4. See below:

- (i) $\frac{42614}{11} = 3874 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;*
- (ii) $\frac{42614}{4} = 10653.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 11;*
- (iii) $\frac{42614}{2} = 21307 \implies$ equal blocks of order 22.*

This implies that we can make **block-wise** construction of magic square of order 44, where the blocks of orders 4 and 22 are of equal magic sums. In case of blocks of order 11, we shall have magic square of order 44 with different magic sums of order 11. In order to construct magic squares of order 44, we need the magic squares of order 4, 11 and 22. The magic square of order 4 and 11 is given in Examples 2.2 and 2.11. The magic squares of 22 can be seen in author's work [17].

Result 37. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 44 are as follows:*

1. **121 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 44 is constructed with 121 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4;*
2. **16 Blocks of Order 11:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 44 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 11;*
3. **4 Blocks of Order 22:** *The magic square of order 44 is constructed with 4 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 22.*

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38 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 45

In this section, we shall present four different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 45. The first as 225 blocks of magic square order 3 of equal sums. The second as 81 blocks of magic squares of order 5 with equal magic sums. The third as 25 blocks of magic squares of order 9 with equal magic sums. The fourth as 9 blocks of magic squares of order 15 with equal magic sums.

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 45 is given by

$$S_{45 \times 45} := \frac{45 \times (1 + 45^2)}{2} = 45585.$$

We can write $45585 := 3 \times 3 \times 5 \times 1013$. This gives the possibility of division by 3, 5, 9 and 15. Let's see the divisions of 45585 by 15, 9, 5 and 3. See below:

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & \frac{45585}{15} = 3039 \quad \implies \quad \text{equal blocks of order 3;} \\ (ii) \quad & \frac{45585}{9} = 5065 \quad \implies \quad \text{equal blocks of order 5;} \\ (iii) \quad & \frac{45585}{5} = 9117 \quad \implies \quad \text{equal blocks of order 9;} \\ (iv) \quad & \frac{45585}{3} = 15195 \quad \implies \quad \text{equal blocks of order 15.} \end{aligned}$$

This implies that we can make **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of order 45 with equal magic sums blocks of orders 3, 5, 9 and 15. In order to produce these magic squares of order 45, we need magic squares of order 3, 5, 9 and 15. The magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 9 are already given in Examples 2.1, 2.3 and 2.8 respectively. The blocks of order 15 are not done as it is included in the case of the order 5 giving equal sums magic squares of order 45. This covers the possibility of blocks of order 15. In case of blocks of order 3, we will get equal sums of **semi-magic** squares. Since order 3 gives semi-magic sums, we shall work with two types of order 9. One of equal magic sums and another with different magic sums.

38.1 Blocks of Order 3

Example 38.1. *The block-wise pan diagonal magic square of order 45 with semi-magic blocks of order 3 is given by*

Result 38. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares of order 45 are as follows:*

- 1. 225 Blocks of Order 3:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 45 is constructed with 225 blocks of equal semi-magic square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
- 2. 81 Blocks of Order 5:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 45 is constructed with 81 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic square of order 5;*
- 3. 25 Blocks of Order 9a:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 45 is constructed with 25 blocks of pandiagonal magic square of order 9 with different magic sums. Each block of order 9 is with semi-magic magic squares of order 3 with equal semi-magic sums.*
- 4. 25 Blocks of Order 9b:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 45 is constructed with 25 blocks of magic square of order 9 with equal magic sums. Blocks of order 3 are with equal sums entries.*
- 5. 9 Blocks of Order 15:** *In this case, the pandiagonal, magic square of order 45 is with blocks of pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums. Each block of order 15 is with equal sums semi-magic squares of order 3.*

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39 Block-Bordered Magic Square of Order 46

The block-bordered magic square of order 46 is constructed in 10 different ways. These are based on block-wise magic squares of order 44, 42 and 40 given in Examples 37.1, 37.2, 37.3, 35.1, 35.2, 35.3, 35.4, 33.1, 33.2 and 33.3.

39.1 Blocks of Order 4: Magic Square of Order 44

Example 39.1. *The block-bordered magic square of order 46 with inner part as pandiagonal magic square of order 44 with blocks of order 4 is given by*

Result 39. *The block-bordered magic square of order 46 is written in ten different ways by use of block-wise magic squares of orders 44, 42 and 40. In case of order 40, one of the possibility is with bimagic square of order 40. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 44, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 44, where blocks of order 11 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums;*
3. *Magic square of order 42, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums;*
4. *Magic square of order 42, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
5. *Magic square of order 42, where blocks of order 7 are magic squares with different magic sums;*
6. *Magic square of order 42, where blocks of order 14 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
7. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 40, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
8. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 40, where blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums;*
9. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 40, where blocks of order 8 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums. In this case, the magic square of order 40 is also a bimagic square, where blocks of order 8 are either bimagic or semi-bimagic with different bimagic or semi-bimagic sums;*
10. *Magic square of order 40, where blocks of order 10 are magic squares with equal magic sums.*

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Result 40. *The block-bordered magic square of order 47 is written in five different ways by use of block-wise magic square of order 45. The block-wise details are as follows:*

1. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums;*
2. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
3. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where blocks of order 9 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums;*
4. *Pandiagonal magic square of order 45, where blocks of order 15 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums.*

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41 Final Remarks

1. We worked only up to order 47, because we used all the **block-wise** magic squares in the constructions **block-bordered** magic squares. See below the table:

Block-Bordered Magic Squares: Orders	Block-Wise Magic Squares Applied: Orders
10	8
11 and 13	8
14	12
17 and 19	15
22	20, 18 and 16
23	21
26	24
29 and 31	27 and 25
34	32, 30 and 28
37	35
38	36
41 and 43	39
46	44, 42 and 40
47	45

2. Further planning is to work with magic squares of order 48 to 62. In this case we shall use magic squares orders 48, 50, 52, 54 and 56 for the block-bordered magic squares of order 58. Magic squares of orders 49 and 51 shall be used for the magic squares of order 53. Orders 55, 57 shall be used for the magic squares of orders 59 and 61. For 62 we shall used order 60. In this way the sequence 48 to 62 is complete. See the table below:

Block-Bordered Magic Squares: Orders	Block-Wise Magic Squares Applied: Orders
53	51 and 49
58	56, 54, 52, 50 and 48
59 and 61	57 and 55
62	60

3. Finally, we observe that any magic square from order 8 onwards, can always be written either **block-wise** or **block-bordered**. The **block-wise** magic square can also be written as **block-bordered** too.

4. Final aim is to reach up to order 108 [10].

42 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

References

- [1] C.A. Pickover, The Zen of Magic Squares, Circles, and Stars, Princeton University Press, 2002.
- [2] G. Pfeffermann, Les Tablettes du Chercheur, Journal des Jeux d'Esprit et de Combinaisons, (fortnightly magazine) issues of 1891 Paris.
- [3] A. L. Candy, Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Composite Order, Lincoln, Neb., 1941.
- [4] H. Derksen, C. Eggrmont and A. Essen, Multimagic Squares, The American Mathematical Monthly, Vol. 114, N 8, October 2007, pages 703-713. Also in <http://arxiv.org/abs/math.CO/0504083>.
- [5] Dwane H. Campbell and Keith A. Campbell, WELCOME TO MAGIC CUBE GENERATOR, <http://magictesseract.com>.
- [6] H. Heinz - Magic Squares, Magic Stars and Other Patterns, <http://www.magicsquares.net>.
- [7] H. White, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
- [8] H. White, Block Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BlockSquares.html>
- [9] H. White, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/SODLS.html>

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

- [10] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [11] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 4k, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [12] Inder J. Taneja, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.

- [13] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [14] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [15] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [16] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.

● Bordered Magic Squares

- [17] Inder J. Taneja, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.
- [18] Inder J. Taneja, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [19] Inder J. Taneja, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.
- [20] Inder J. Taneja, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [21] Inder J. Taneja, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.
- [22] Inder J. Taneja, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>.

● Block-Bordered Magic Squares

- [23] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [24] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.

[25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.

● **Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares**

[26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares With Magic Sums 21, 21^2 and 2021. **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-118, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4380343>.
